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Practical Aspects for the Module Selection of Modern Wireless Infotainment Systems

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Abstract - This Paper discusses about the selection of modules for a typical wireless infotainment system that supports applications like Bluetooth, WLAN, and Mobile TV for entertainment, education and information. Section 1 brief about the trends and approach for the selection of wireless modules. Section 2 outlines the important parameters to be considered for module selection. Section 3 gives a practical understanding for vendor selection criterion. Section 4 outlines best module selection for particular application on the basis of trade-off analysis and evaluation of reference designs. Section 5 concludes this paper.

Index Terms— Wireless infotainment, Bluetooth, WLAN, Mobile TV

1. Introduction

The Infotainment Devices are being conceptualized as convergent devices that combine navigation and infotainment requirements on a single “portable” platform. Today innovation and technology convergence are driving the changes in the auto market. Consumers are now demanding advanced infotainment systems and solutions for their vehicles. New services such as GPS live mobile TV, terrestrial TV, FM radio, Bluetooth, and access to the Wi-Fi network for internet access, emails, and chats etc. are getting implemented in vehicles. This paper discusses about the practical aspects for the module selection for GPS, Bluetooth, WLAN, Mobile TV, Terrestrial TV and FM Radio for a typical wireless infotainment system. Different available modules are compared on the basis of capabilities of the modules for the different wireless applications and best suitable modules are selected.

2. Fundamental Parameters to Understand for Module Selection

The below block diagram shows the high level Architecture and the Input Output connectivity / ports of a typical wireless infotainment system. This is used as a reference for the High Level design of the system based on the commercially available Systems on Chip. This product integrates a various modern wireless navigation and entertainment technologies such as GPS, Bluetooth, WLAN, Mobile TV, Terrestrial TV and FM Radio.

Figure. 1. Diagram of a Typical Wireless Infotainment System

Wireless infotainment industry is looking for every possibility to trim the size of the components of their products and increase more functionalities, then the best approach is to use integrated RF modules readily available in the market rather than using individual components (such as PA, duplexer, transceivers etc.) with out any compromise in their performance. Integrated modules lowers the time to market and design efforts, they come preassembled and tested with optimized internal interfaces reducing the chance for design errors with optimum performance. To Gain competitive advantages to develop system quickly and cost efficiently, one should use readily available modules from third party vendors. Selection of modules or components for any wireless device requires knowledge of some fundamental parameters. Nonetheless, although the availability of off-the-shelf components, modules and reference designs has made wireless infotainment system design a little easier, the designer still needs to acquire some fundamental knowledge about the parameters that influence in the selection of modules.

2.1 Important Parameters for GPS Module Selection

In this section we will discuss about the aspects of important parameters to be considered for GPS module selection

TABLE 1. Important parameters for GPS module selection

Type	Parameters	Unit
Receiver	Receiver Channels	NA
	Acquisition Sensitivity	dBm
	Tracking Sensitivity	dBm
	Time to first fix	seconds
	Positioning accuracy	meter
	NMEA support	NA
DC	Power Consumption	mW
General	Dimensions	mm ²
	Driver support	NA
	Cost	NA

As per requirement specifications module selection for GPS receiver is aimed for selecting best performance characteristics such as lower power consumption, tracking of weak satellites, faster acquisition times and more accurate position fixes. GPS receivers specify two sensitivity values, acquisition sensitivity and tracking sensitivity.

Acquisition sensitivity represents the lowest power level at which a receiver will be able to achieve a position fix. Tracking sensitivity is the lowest power level at which a receiver will be able to track an individual satellite and is measured by measuring the C/N ratio of a receiver for a known input power level. For a typical GPS receiver minimum C/N ratio is 28 to 32 dB-Hz to achieve a position fix. A receiver requires at least four satellites to obtain a 3D position fix and Time to first fix gives the details regarding time required for a GPS receiver to acquire satellite signals and navigation data, and calculate a position fix. TTFF requirement for this typical GPS receiver is < 1 Sec. positioning accuracy of a GPS receiver is expressed in a specific coordinate system such as latitude and longitude and gives the ability of a receiver to accurately locate your position. Positioning accuracy requirement for this typical GPS receiver is <5m. One should also consider other parameters such as NMEA support is a standard used by the GPS receiver to transmit data, receiver channels, power consumption, Dimensions and price for selection of modules for this typical GPS receiver.

2.2 Important Parameters for Bluetooth and WLAN Module Selection

In this section we will discuss about the aspects of important parameters to be considered for Bluetooth and WLAN module selection

TABLE 2. Important parameters for Bluetooth and WLAN module selection

Type	Parameters	Unit
Transmitter	Max RF Transmit Power	dBm
	20 dB bandwidth for modulated carrier	MHz
Receiver	Receiver sensitivity	dBm
	Receiver dynamic range	dB
	Co-channel rejection	dB
	Adjacent channel selectivity	dB
	Mirror image attenuation	dB
DC	Total Power Consumption	mW
General	Maximum data rate	Mbps/ Kbps
	Driver support	NA

The Maximum Transmitter Power and Sensitivity are critical parameters to consider for bluetooth and WLAN module selection. They directly play role in transmission budget analysis, do have an affect on transmission reliability, especially when two transmitters like Bluetooth and WLAN are working in the same free license band and are in close proximity. Maximum transmit power determines the range for bluetooth and WLAN devices [1] as an example approximate range of an Bluetooth device with respect to the maximum transmit is listed below in table3:

TABLE. 3. Table for bluetooth device range with respect to the maximum output power

Class	Maximum Transmitted Power	Range(Approximate)
Class1	20 dBm	~100 meters
Class2	4 dBm	~10 meters
Class3	1 dBm	~1 meters

One has to ensure that the radio can operate over its stated range in number of different operating conditions, at stated output power and sensitivity and in different environmental conditions such as air humidity, obstacles such as people and furniture etc. and one should also ensure that the sensitivity stated in the datasheet is at maximum data rate as sensitivity degrades as data rate increases. The DC Power consumption is important parameter especially when one is selecting components for handheld products. The need for the low DC power consumption is to improve the battery life of the system, lower will be the DC power consumption better will be battery life.

The maximum data rate for bluetooth EDR device is 3 Mbps and for WLAN 802.11a,802.11b/g is 11 Mbps and 54 Mbps respectively but it depends on driver's / interface data rate also. Coexistence of Bluetooth module in close proximity with WLAN modules affects the performance parameters such as range; data rate. Testing the interference of a Bluetooth system against a WLAN in a close proximity has been studied. As the result, it is revealed that the throughput of Bluetooth decreases as the disturbance wave level increases, and communication between the Bluetooth slave and the Bluetooth master node is interrupted due to Wi-Fi module with several channels [3]. One could install a small setup to ensure the range, data rate stated by the vendor as an example please find below a basic small setup for performance measurement of WLAN module without using any sophisticated equipments like Signal generators, spectrum analyzers.

Figure. 2. Basic setup for WLAN data rate and range testing

The first step is to have the Client associate with the Access Point. Next the IPERF utility is invoked on both the Client and the server side of the connection. The DOS based IPERF utility is used to initiate data transfers between the Client and the server. On the Client side the IPERF utility is invoked to run in Client mode using the command .Once the Client and the server have associated, and the IPERF utility is running on both of them, it continuously outputs the measured data rate and by changing the distance between client and server one can calculate the range for DUT. The other receiver as well as transmitter parameters are not directly part of the transmission link budget analysis but they have an effect on transmission performance and one should also consider that parameters for module selection.

2.3 Important Parameters for Mobile TV Module Selection

In this section we will discuss about the aspects of important parameters to be considered for Mobile TV module selection

TABLE 4. Important parameters for mobile TV module selection

Type	Parameters	Unit
Receiver	Receiver sensitivity	dBm
	Receiver dynamic range	dB
	Co-channel rejection	dB
	Adjacent channel selectivity	dB
	Mirror image attenuation	dB
DC	Total Power Consumption	mW
General	Supported Standards	NA
	Supported Bands	NA
	Supported Drivers	NA
	Supported Middleware	NA

As we have already discussed most of the receiver, DC parameter aspects in the previous section 2.1. In this section we will discuss about the aspects of general parameters of Mobile TV application. The mobile TV industry is fragmented with different markets supporting different standards and different bands such as DVB-H has a strong hold in Europe and is also to be the dominant standard in south east Asia –Taiwan, Singapore, Vietnam, Malaysia-and the Pacific Rim, Media Flo seems to be the winner in North America, ISDB-T will dominate in Japan, Brazil and couple other south American countries, south Korea is dominated by T-DMB and in china home grown standard known as CMMB(S-TIMI) will be the main platform for Mobile TV. Being the picture so unclear one should select the mobile TV component that could be able to support multi standards and multiband solution so, that migration effort and time from one standard to other standards will reduce i.e. a very few hardware changes is needed, a single module can be used to support multiple standards. The drivers are used to initialize the chip, tune to given channel and to handle mobility aspects like band scan and handover and the Middleware includes upper layer functionality like IP stack, Electronic Service Guide extraction, parsing and decompression, multi channel support for Picture in Picture and Watch/Record, conditional access, clip casting, file delivery, and A/V decoder interface. One should ensure from the respective vendor regarding the availability of drivers and middleware features while selecting components.

2.4 Important Parameters for Analog TV Module Selection

In this section we will discuss about the aspects of important parameters to be considered for Analog TV module selection

TABLE 5. Important parameters for Analog TV module selection

Type	Parameters	Unit
Receiver	Receiver sensitivity	dBm
	Adjacent channel selectivity	dB
DC	Total Power Consumption	mW
General	Supported Standards	NA
	Supported Bands	NA
	Supported Drivers	NA
	Dimensions	mm ³
	Price	NA

Sensitivity is the ability of a tuner to pick up weak analog TV signals. The higher the sensitivity, the better the tuner's ability to bring in weaker stations clearly. Adjacent channel selectivity is the ability of the receiver to select the wanted signal and to reject the unwanted signal such as another broadcast in adjacent frequency channels. Supported bands for analog TV is NTSC, PAL and SECAM. NTSC standard is used in most of the America, Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, the Philippines, Burma and some pacific island nations. PAL standard is used in Europe, Ireland, Hong Kong, Macau, Mainland of China, India, Australia, Brazil and Argentina. SECAM standard is used in for global coverage Russia, Ukraine and portions of Middle East & Africa. Based on the coverage of standards, NTSC and PAL are considered as a primary standard for module selection.

2.5 Important Parameters for FM Radio Module Selection

In this section we will discuss about the aspects of important parameters to be considered for FM module selection

TABLE 6. Important parameters for FM radio module selection

Type	Parameters	Unit
Receiver	RDS Support	NA
	Sensitivity	dBm
	RDS Sensitivity	dBm
	Total Harmonic Distortion	dB
	Maximum signal to noise ratio	dB
DC	Total Power Consumption	mW
General	Supported Bands	NA
	Supported Drivers	NA
	Dimensions	NA
	Cost	NA

RDS and RBDS is a communication protocol for European broadcast union and US broadcast respectively for sending digital information using conventional FM radio broadcast such as time, track / artist information and station identification. Sensitivity is the ability of a tuner to pick up FM radio transmitters. The higher the sensitivity, the better the tuner's ability to bring in weaker stations clearly. The sensitivity figure indicates the tuner's ability to pull in a moderately distant station mostly noise-free and in stereo. The lower the number, the better the reception of the FM radio. The total harmonic distortion (THD) of a signal is a measurement of the harmonic distortion present, that is, any deviation of the actual output signal with respect to the ideal transfer function. Signal to noise ratio (SNR) is a measurement indicating the difference in dB between the level of the background noise and the level of the signal. The higher the number, the better the signal to noise ratio and the lesser the background noise from the tuner.

3. Vendor Selection Criterion

A general criterion of selection of vendors in modern wireless infotainment area is listed below:

- **Vendors Experience:** There are branded vendors who are more experienced and established in wireless infotainment components with a decent technical support. Depending on experience base and availability of resources to support wireless infotainment projects, one should select the type of vendor. Second most important consideration is whether the vendor has knowledge of business processes in the specific domain e.g. Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Mobile TV, etc. Each industry has unique requirements and vendors should have figured out how their product or service handles these industry-specific issues.
- **Track Record of vendors in Wireless infotainment Services:** In an emerging industry, it is extremely important to take into account the track record of the vendor in servicing its clients. There are many vendors in wireless infotainment industry who have large, experienced and lots of customers but are just entering this industry. On the other hand, there may be an experienced, small vendor who has the right product and service.
- **Avoid Risk for selecting a new component and startup Vendor:** There are risks and corresponding rewards in working with a new component and startup vendors such as the problem of stability of the components parameters in the rigorous conditions. One should ensure the stability of the components from technical datasheets, application notes and evaluating reference designs for particular components and as a reward one can negotiate component and source code at lower price. It is a matter of tradeoffs.
- **Price:** This obviously plays an important role when making a decision on what products to purchase. A wireless component with a higher price, though, could be the best one to choose. As a result, a careful consideration is to be made for the installation and support tools which a higher priced component might include'. It could be worth the extra money if the higher priced component saves considerable time when integrating this component with the system.
- **Availability:** Even though a vendor may have a particular product on the market, they may have difficulty fulfilling the order in time. This is especially true if someone is purchasing a new component, consider availability when comparing vendors.

4. Module Selection

One can use the above mentioned criterion and fundamental parameters stated in datasheets of particular vendors. A list of the top wireless vendors is considered and selected a preferred vendor who satisfies all our requirements. Also evaluate several products are evaluated before making a final decision. For example, one could install a small test setup in a lab to compare the performance of top three vendors. There's nothing better than a live comparison, but one has to be sure to judge them equally using common test conditions and criteria. In this section we will discuss about GPS, Bluetooth, WLAN, Mobile TV, Analog TV and FM radio module selection and for that a Comparison with respect to different vendors / Modules are done and a comparison table is prepared. This table consists of all important parameters illustrated in section 2 and 3 for respective applications.

4.1 GPS Module Selection

TABLE 7. Comparison Table for GPS module selection

Type	Parameters	Wi2Wi	Fastrax	Micro module
		W2SG0004	IT321	MN5010HS
Receiver	Frequency Band Receiver Type Acquisition Sensitivity Tracking Sensitivity Time to First Fix Positioning Accuracy NMEA Support	1.575 GHz 20 Channels -141 dBm -157 dBm 0.6Sec 3 m Yes	1.575 GHz 20 Channels NM -159 dBm < 1 Sec NM Yes	1.575 GHz 20 Channels -142 dBm -159dBm < 1 Sec < 2.5 m Yes
DC	Power Consumption	3.3 V ; 50 mA	3.3 V ; 45 mA	3.3V ; 46 mA
General	Interface Support Dimensions ROHS Compliant Price	UART 11.2mm×12mm×2.5mm Yes 100K pcs : \$13.06	UART 10.4mm×14mm×2.3 mm NM 100K pcs : \$14.9	UART 10mm×10mm×1.8mm Yes 100K pcs : \$16.0

As per datasheet Parameters such as tracking sensitivity, acquisition sensitivity, and positioning accuracy are approximately equal for all the three vendors. Time to first fix is lowest for the W2SG004 module. Size and Pricing are also lowest for the W2SG004 module. Also all the three vendors are evaluated before making a final decision and it is found that performance wise all the three are approximately equal. Based on remaining parameters like Price and Size and considering other parameters such as availability of modules and evaluation boards W2SG004 module is selected for the GPS application.

4.2 Bluetooth and WLAN Module Selection

Blue tooth and WLAN operating in same frequency range of 2.4GHz. So it will create interference problems between both of these. But, some vendors provides solution which supports simultaneous functionality of Bluetooth and WLAN and this solution is called 'coexistence' technique; in this technique software monitors WLAN and Bluetooth traffic patterns and, when both 802.11 and Bluetooth require bandwidth, it uses multiplexing techniques to allocate the bandwidth for simultaneous functions. In this way, RF interference between 802.11 and Bluetooth is eliminated, packet collisions are avoided and high throughput rates are maintained without requiring antenna isolation. Then, better approach is to use single modules which support coexistence of Bluetooth and WLAN.

TABLE 8. Comparison Table for Bluetooth and WLAN module selection

Type	Parameters	Jorjin	Wi2Wi	USI
		WG7210	W2CBW003	WM-BG-MR-03
Transmitter	Max RF Transmit Power for Bluetooth	+ 3 dBm	+ 3 dBm	+ 3 dBm
Receiver	Max RF Transmit Power for WLAN 20 dB bandwidth for modulated carrier	+ 20 dBm	+ 20 dBm	+ 15 dBm
	Receiver sensitivity for bluetooth Receiver sensitivity for WLAN Receiver dynamic range	720 KHz	720 KHz	720 KHz
	Co-channel rejection Adjacent channel selectivity Mirror image attenuation	-93 dBm @ 3 Mbps -80 dBm @ 54 Mbps >10 dBm	-89 dBm @ 3 Mbps -73dBm @ 54 dBm >10 dBm	-79 dBm @ 3 Mbps -70dBm @ 54 dBm >10 dBm
	Rx Power Consumption for	12 dB 30 dB 35 dB	14 dB 30 dB 35 dB	12 dB 30 dB 35 Db
	DC	Tx Power Consumption for Maximum data rate	195mW @ Bluetooth, 295 mW @ WLAN, 550mW @ Bluetooth	215mW @ Bluetooth, 400mW @ WLAN 550mW @ Bluetooth

General	Driver support	1.4 Mbps @ Bluetooth, 18.6 Mbps @ WLAN	1.3 Mbps @ Bluetooth, 16.2 Mbps @ WLAN	1.0 Mbps @ Bluetooth, 15.4 Mbps @ WLAN
	Price	UART,SDIO	UART,SDIO	UART,SDIO
	Dimensions	\$ 11.3@10 K 12mm×13mm×1.65mm	\$ 14.25@10 K 12mm×12mm×1.4mm	\$18.0@10K 12.5mm×12.5mm×1.3mm

As shown in table 8, the top three vendors that support single modules with coexistence technique for Bluetooth and WLAN has been considered for comparison and among all, Vendor 1 is selected because of best pricing, receiver sensitivity and data rate for both Bluetooth and WLAN .

4.3 Mobile TV Module Selection

TABLE 9. Comparison Table for Mobile TV Component selection

Type	Parameters	Siano	New Port Media	DIBcom
		SMS1130	NMI310 / NMI700 / NMI320	DIB9080H / DIB8076M
Receiver	Receiver sensitivity	-98 dBm	-97 dBm	-98 dBm
	Receiver dynamic range	>2dBm	>3dBm	>3dBm
	Co-channel rejection	12 dB	12dB	12dB
	Adjacent channel selectivity	35dB	32 dB	34dB
	Mirror image attenuation	39dB	35dB	36dB
DC	Total Power Consumption	200mW	195 mW	200mW
General	Supported Standards	DVB-H/T,ISDB-T,T-	DVB-H/T	ISDB-T
	Supported Bands	DMB	VHF/UHF/L	VHF/UHF/L
	Supported Drivers	VHF/UHF/L	SPI	SPI
	Supported Middleware Features	SPI	ESG/EPG,PIP,PVR	ESG/EPG,PIP,PVR
	Price	ESG/EPG,PIP,PVR \$ 8.73 @ 10 K	\$8.0 @ 10 K	\$8.0@10K

The greatest challenge for Mobile TV module selection is to get a single module that should support multiple standards so, that migration effort and time from one standard to other standards will reduce i.e., a very few hardware changes is needed , a single module can be used to support multiple standards. As shown in table 5 Siano SMS1130 price is high than other two vendors and other RF parameters are approximately same even though vendor 1 got selected for this application because it supports multi- standards.

4.4 Analog TV Module Selection

TABLE 10. Comparison Table for Analog TV Component selection

Type	Parameters	Telegent Systems	Telegent Systems	Telegent Systems
		TLG1130	TLG1120	TLG1100
Receiver	Frequency Band	48 – 862 MHz	48 – 862 MHz	48 – 862 MHz
	Receiver sensitivity	-100 dBm	-102dBm	-102dBm
	Adjacent channel selectivity	75dBc	80dBc	80dBc
DC	Total Power Consumption	250mW	250mW	250mW
General	Supported Standards	DVB-H/DVB-T/NTSC/PAL/FM	NTSC/PAL/SECAM/FM	NTSC/PAL/FM
	Supported Drivers	SDIO / SPI		
	ROHS Compliant	Yes	I2C	I2C
	Dimensions	10×10 mm	Yes	Yes
	Price	\$ 9.0 @ 100 K Pcs	7×7 mm \$ 8.89 @ 100 K Pcs	8×8 mm \$ 8.89 @ 100 K Pcs

For handheld wireless infotainment system size and height of the module is one of the important parameter for the selection of modules. For Analog TV application only Telegent Systems is found suitable for providing required size of the module, other vendor modules are found bulky and bigger in size and suitable for consumer electronics products such as DVD players etc. As shown in Table 10 form factor for TLG1120 is lowest among all the three modules, SECAM addition for global coverage Russia, Ukraine and portions of Middle East & Africa. TLG1100 are not having this Feature.TLG1120 share the same antenna for both Analog TV and FM radio eliminating the need for a more involved FM input match design based upon the variable load of a headphone cable. Additionally, if the FM stereo function shares the TV antenna than a more expensive headphone cable with grounding/shielding is eliminated. Sharing the antenna between TV and FM also benefits the end-consumer as usage case studies have shown that consumers often do not carry the headphone cable with them, forget it, or lose it thus invalidating the ability to use the FM stereo feature. Based on the above discussed parameters TLG1120 is selected for Analog TV application.

4.5 FM Radio Module Selection

TABLE 11. Comparison Table for FM Radio Module selection

Type	Parameters	Philips	Silicon Labs	Sigmatel (Free scale)
		TEA5990HN/UK	Si4703	STFM1000
Receiver	Frequency Band	70 – 108 MHz	76 – 108 MHz	76 – 108 MHz
	RDS / RBDS Demodulation	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Sensitivity	-106 dBm	-100dBm	104.7dBm
	RDS Sensitivity	-86.16dBm	-83.5dBm	NM
	TH	0.5%	0.5%	0.06%
DC	Power Consumption	40.5mW	NM	35 mW
General	Supported Bands	European / US / Japanese / China Band	European / US / Japanese	European / US / Japanese
	Supported Drivers	I2C	I2C	I2C
	Dimensions	4×4×1.0 mm	3×3×0.5 mm	5×5×1.0 mm
	Price	\$1.2 @ 10 K Pcs	\$ 2.07 @ 10K Pcs	--

As shown in Table 11 Sigmatel STFM1000 power consumption and Total harmonic distortion is lowest among all the vendors but this module is not compatible with TI OMAP3430 processor though it got rejected. Receiver sensitivity and RDS demodulator sensitivity for Philips TEA5660HN/UK is better than Silicon labs Si47403 and pricing is also less .So Philips TEA5990HN/UK got selected for FM radio application.

5. Conclusion

Understanding how different components parameters influence a wireless performance link is essential in building a perfect wireless infotainment system. By knowing the operation and aspects of the fundamental wireless parameters such as maximum RF transmit power, receiver sensitivity, power consumption, pricing and availability, the comparison is done and on the basis comparison results the best solution for the Bluetooth ,WLAN and Mobile TV is selected for wireless infotainment system. Not to forget here, component and module selection trade-off is one of the key aspects in the whole product development phase which is linked to the performance of the product.

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